

Design and planning strategies for development of public sport in Kohgiluyeh & BoyerAhmad province

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Abstract

Purpose of this research was to design and planning strategies for development of public sport in Kohgiluyeh and BoyerAhmad province. The statistical population was all experts and sport managers of this province that 30 people were selected to this research with purposive sampling method. The present research tool was Delphi technique. Data analysis was performed by the descriptive and inferential statistics and internal and external assessment matrix. The results showed that both total scores of internal and external factors matrix is less than 2.5. Accordingly to these results, Women's public sport in Kohgiluyeh and BoyerAhmad province was in WT region. Therefore, the aim of the strategy must to decrease weakness organization and avoiding of environmental threats.

Key words: Public sport, Strategy, Development, SWOT, Kohgiluyeh & Boyerahmad province

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